

POROUS PDMS/CNFS COMPOSITES FOR STRETCHABLE STRAIN SENSORS

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ABSTRACT

Strain sensors with flexible and stretchable characteristics have shown great potential applications in wearable devices for artificial e-skins and health monitoring/diagnosis. However, there remain some major challenges to develop sensors capable of both high sensitivity and stretchability by using a simple, cost-effective, and scalable method. In this paper, we report a new and facile method to fabricate porous polydimethylsiloxane/carbon nanofiber (p-PDMS/CNFs) composites using sugar particles coated with carbon nanofibers as the templates. Three-dimensional porous conductive PDMS nanocomposites are prepared by first infusing the templates with PDMS, curing the PDMS, and then removing sugar. The CNFs originally coated on the surfaces of sugar particles are embedded in PDMS pore walls, forming 3D conductive networks, resulting in high electrical conductivity (0.033 S/m). The resulting three-dimensional porous structure demonstrates greatly improved stretchability and compressibility compared with solid PDMS. The electrical resistance of the porous composites increases upon stretching but decreases under compression. Moreover, it is found that the resultant nanocomposites with the CNFs embedded in pore walls show excellent durability under repeated loading. The high sensitivity and reliable sensing performance endow these highly stretchable nanocomposites with a great potential as flexible sensors for wearable electronics.

1 INTRODUCTION

There is a growing demand for the wearable electronics in the past decade due to their potential applications in real-time healthcare monitoring [1-2], electronic skins [3], human-friendly interactive electronics [4], and flexible and foldable displays [5]. Flexible conductors and strain sensors such as an organic field-effect transistor, piezoelectric sensor, capacitive and piezoresistive sensor are the key components of wearable electronics [6]. Among these different types of sensors, piezoresistive sensors based on resistance change have attracted considerable attention since it requires relatively simple read-out system. Conventional metallic strain gauge has gauge factor of around 2.0 and strain limit of around ~ 5% which is far less than that required for being used in wearable electronics. For instance, the movement of human joints upon stretching and contracting can generate large strains up to 55%. Therefore, flexible and stretchable conductive polymer nanocomposites with conductive nanofillers

that are embedded or distributed spatially in polymer matrices have been extensively investigated as substitutes for traditional rigid metallic foil strain gauges [1-3].

Conductive nanomaterials such as nanowires [7], carbon nanotubes [8], carbon nanofibers (CNFs) [9], metal nanoparticles [10], and graphene [1-2] have been combined with elastic polymers to achieve a high level of stretchability and electrical conductivity. Particularly, nanoscale carbon with excellent mechanical and electrical properties has demonstrated attractive performance when being used in flexible sensors and conductors. To achieve high electrical conductivity, the loading of nanofillers should reach its percolation thresholds so that conductive network is formed in the composites. Variation of the conductive networks under strain and intrinsic piezoresistivity of the nanofillers cause the changes of resistance, which endows piezoresistivity in the nanocomposites. Alternatively, buckypaper sensors consisting of carbon nanotubes, carbon nanofibers, graphene, or their hybrids have been developed [11]. Recently, researchers have shown that arranging the carbon nanomaterials into three-dimensional (3D) interconnected structures such as aerogels or foams is a promising strategy to greatly improve the electrical conductivity at a much lower loading [6, 12-13]. Polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) nanocomposites based on 3D graphene foam/aerogel have demonstrated high piezoresistive sensitivity with a gauge factor (GF) being as high as 99. Nevertheless, such sensors have relatively poor deformation capability (maximum failure strain is approximately 30%), which largely limits their applications [6].

To improve the deformability, recent research has demonstrated that, by introducing 3D interconnected porous structure, the failure strain of elastomers can be greatly extended beyond their intrinsic limit of bulk counterparts [14-17]. Park et al [17] showed that 3D nanostructured pores can be introduced into PDMS by photolithography technique, which increases the fracture strain by 225% over its solid counterpart. More recently, porous PDMS has been developed by using different sacrificial templates including 3D printed polymers or nickel foams [15, 18]. These templates are usually removed by time-consuming etching process with toxic solvents. To overcome these issues, eco-friendly and cost-effective templates such as sodium chloride or sugar cubes have been investigated to fabricate porous structures [14, 19]. Stretchable conductive polymer nanocomposites are thus developed by infiltrating conductive materials into the porous elastic matrices or fabricating thin-layer coatings of conductive materials on the surfaces of the 3D-interconnected matrices [16]. However, to improve the mechanical durability, certain special surface treatment is required to facilitate the adhesion of the conductive fillers onto the surface of the pores. For instance, Liang et al have recently reported the fabrication of 3D stretchable, compressible, and highly conductive metal-coated PDMS sponges by surface modification of PDMS with poly[2-(methacryloyloxy)ethyl-trimethylammonium-chloride] followed with electroless metal deposition [14]. It remains highly desirable to develop cost-effective methods to fabricate 3D porous conductive nanocomposites.

In this work, a novel strategy has been developed to fabricate stretchable porous conductive nanocomposites (denoted by p-PDMS/CNFs) by using CNFs-coated sugar particles as the pore-creating agent. CNFs are firstly coated onto sugar particles surfaces which are then used as the templates. By curing the PDMS and removing the sugar particles, porous PDMS/CNFs composites are obtained. The CNFs originally coated on the surface of sugar particles are transferred and embedded in PDMS pore walls forming conductive network. This new conductive polymer composite shows excellent durability due to the fact that CNFs are embedded within the sub-surface of pores rather than being deposited on the surface of pores. The piezoresistivity under tension and compression are studied and compared, followed by a discussion of the underlying mechanisms responsible for the piezoresistive characteristics of this new type of nanocomposites.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Carbon nanofibers with a diameter of ~ 70–200 nm and a length of ~50–200 μm (Pyrograf®-III, grade PR-24-XT-HHT) were supplied by Applied Sciences Inc. Sylgard 184 silicone elastomer base and curing agent were supplied by Dow Corning Co. Ltd (Australia). Brown sugar with average size of about 225 μm was obtained from local supermarket. Graphene oxide was synthesized by an

improved Hummers' method [13]. The high-purity silver-paste (Silver Paste Plus™) was from SPI Supplies (US).

The strain sensors were fabricated by the procedure illustrated in Figure 1. Different from commonly used dip-coating method, the sugar templates were firstly prepared from sugar particles coated with CNFs. Firstly, CNFs were dispersed in isopropanol with graphene oxide as the dispersant by using a Sonics VCX-750 Vibra Cell Ultra Sonic Processor (40% amplitude, pulse duration: 5 second on, 5 second off). The mass ratio of CNF: graphene oxide is 20:1. After 30 minutes' sonication, no visible aggregates are observed. Then, sugar particles were added to the dispersion (2 mg/mL) to get slurry-like mixture, which was then placed in a vacuum oven to remove the isopropanol. Subsequently, the CNF-coated sugar was pressed into a rectangular template by a hydraulic press. The PDMS prepolymer was mixed with the curing agent by magnetically stirring at a weight ratio of 10:1. After degassing for ~30 minutes, the mixture was poured onto the sugar template. Owing to its low viscosity and low surface energy, PDMS infiltrated gradually into the 3D interconnected open spaces between sugar particles. To facilitate the infiltration process of PDMS, the filled sample was placed in a vacuum oven for 1 h. The PDMS-CNF-sugar mixture was cured at 65 °C for 2 h. The excess PDMS around the sample edges was trimmed away to expose sugar particles which were subsequently removed by immersing into warm water (40 °C) for 3 h and sonicated for 1 h. Finally, a 3D porous PDMS with interconnected CNFs in the pore walls was obtained by drying in a vacuum oven overnight.

Figure 1: a) -f) illustrates the product of each step during the fabrication process of p-PDMS/CNFs nanocomposites.

The morphology of the porous p-PDMS/CNFs nanocomposites were investigated using a scanning electron microscope (a FEI Nova NanoSEM). The nanocomposite specimens were cryogenically fractured in liquid nitrogen and then coated with a thin layer of gold prior to observation.

Specimens with dimensions of 40 mm (length) \times 6 mm (width) \times 1.5 mm (thickness) and 10 mm (length) \times 10 mm (width) \times 8 mm (thickness) were prepared for tension and compression tests, respectively. A universal test machine (Instron Model 4466) was employed to apply compressive and/or tensile force to the nanocomposites. The nanocomposites were tested first under quasi-static and subsequently under cyclic loading-unloading cycles under displacement-control. For the quasi-static test, the strain rate of 8%/min was used. The cyclic tests were conducted by applying a triangular waveform at a frequency of 0.08 Hz. The durability was investigated by stretching/compressing the

nanocomposites from 0% to 30% strain for up to 1000 cycles. The electrical resistance was measured by a digital multimeter (34465A, Keysight Technologies). Thin copper wires were attached to the two ends of the strain sensor using a conductive silver-paste adhesive.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figures 2a-b show SEM images of the CNFs coated sugar particle. It is seen from Figure 2b that the CNFs on the surfaces of sugar particles form an interconnected network. When the liquid PDMS is cast onto the CNFs-coated sugar template, the liquid PDMS diffuses into the sugar templates by capillary forces. Meanwhile, the PDMS spreads into the CNFs network on the surface of the sugar particles, owing to the low viscosity and low surface energy of PDMS [20]. After curing the PDMS, the CNFs are entrapped within the PDMS, near the surfaces of pores. The SEM image of the porous p-PDMS/CNFs (Figure 2c) shows that the PDMS composites consist of a porous, interconnected 3D microstructure, which is the inverse matrix of the sugar template. The size of the pores is determined by the size of the sugar particles, which is estimated to be approximately 225 μm on average. A close-up view of the pore wall (Figure 2d) indicates that the CNFs are mostly embedded within the PDMS and the CNFs are interconnected, resulting in high electrical conductivity.

Figure 2: SEM images of (a) a sugar particle coated with CNFs; (b) CNFs coated on the sugar surface; (c) porous p-PDMS/CNFs; (d) CNFs embedded in pore wall of p-PDMS/CNFs.

To characterise the electromechanical properties, the porous composites p-PDMS/CNFs were firstly subjected to quasi-static compressive and tensile strain from $\epsilon=0\%$ to $\epsilon=80\%$, respectively. The resistance variations are given in Figure 3. It is seen that the resistance increases monotonically with the applied tensile strain. At low strains ($< \sim 30\%$), the relative change in resistance ($\Delta R/R_0$) shows linear relationship with strain. The gauge factor defined as $(\Delta R/R_0)/\epsilon$ is estimated to be around 6.5. At higher strains, the $\Delta R/R_0$ rises exponentially. By contrast, a completely opposite trend in $\Delta R/R_0$ is observed when subjected to compressive strain, as shown in Figure 3b. The resistance decreases linearly with the applied compressive strain up to approximately 45% strain. The gauge factor calculated by linear fitting is around 1.3. Upon further increasing the strain, a second linear region is observed with the slope (gauge factor) of ~ 1.9 , indicating a higher sensitivity in the high strain range. Obviously, the

sensitivity of GPN-PDMS composite is much higher under tension than under compression. This is due to the fact that tensile deformation is more effective at disrupting conductive paths (i.e., breaking contacts) than compressive deformation.

Figure 3: Piezoresistivity of p-PDMS/CNFs: normalized resistance change under static loading: (a) tensile strain and (b) compressive strain.

The porous nanocomposites are subjected to cyclic stretching-releasing to investigate their physical robustness and reliability. Three different strain ranges, 0% to 10%, 0% to 30%, and 0% to 50% were selected for these tests. Figure 4 shows the resistance changes over six cycles with varying levels of peak strain. The $\Delta R/R_0$ increases upon stretching and gradually decreases during unloading. A complete opposite trend is observed under compression: electrical resistance decreases with compressive strain and recover during unloading. The stretching deformation widens the inter-CNFs distance, thus increasing the tunneling resistance and contact resistance. In contrast, under compressive strain, the microstructure changes in the opposite manner, leading to the decrease in electrical resistance. Moreover, the sensors can nearly recover its resistance after unloading. To investigate the long-term performance and stability of the nanocomposite sensors, a reliability test is performed under both compression and tension strain from 0% to 30%. A total of 1,000 tension/release and compression/release cycles were applied to sensors while the response was monitored. The sensor shows a stable and reliable performance to the cyclic loading/unloading, as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 4: Normalized resistance change under six cyclic (a) stretching-releasing and (b) compressing-releasing loadings.

Figure 5: Durability test on the nanocomposites sensors: the sensor was stretched and compressed to $\epsilon=30\%$ and released to $\epsilon=0\%$ for up to 1,000 cycles.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Conductive porous PDMS/CNFs nanocomposites (p-PDMS/CNFs) have been developed via a new, cost-effective method using CNFs-coated sugar particles as the templates. The CNFs coated on the surface of sugar particles are transferred to the pore walls of PDMS, forming a thin layer of conductive nanocomposites. The piezoresistivity of the p-PDMS/CNFs has been investigated by applying compressive and tensile strains to the nanocomposites. It is found that the electric resistance increases monotonically with the applied tensile strain and decreases under compressive strain. The piezoresistivity of p-PDMS/CNFs arises dominantly from the variation of tunneling resistance and contact resistance. The durability test results indicate that the nanocomposites sensors show stable and reliable sensing performance. The high sensitivity and reliable sensing performance, in addition to the facile and cost-effective fabrication protocol, endow these highly stretchable nanocomposites with a great potential as flexible sensors for wearable electronics.

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